

Molecular and Bacteriological Study of Vancomycin Resistant *Staphylococcus Aureus* (VRSA) Isolated from Buffalo Raw Milk in Baghdad

Zahraa Kadhim lafi¹, Rana Mahmood Ahmad², Hisham Alshaikhli³

¹Department of Zoonotic Disease, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Baghdad, Baghdad, Iraq.

²Department of Physiology, Biochemistry and Pharmacology, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Baghdad, Baghdad, Iraq

³Department of Basic Medical Sciences – College of Nursing – Qatar University, Doha, Qatar

¹ Orcid.ID: 0000-0002-2074-3990

² Orcid.ID:0000-0002-7563-7132

³ Orcid.ID: 0000-0001-8413-7060

ABSTRACT

One hundred buffalo raw milk samples from different locations in Baghdad governorate, Iraq, were tested for Vancomycin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (VRSA) by streaking on a plate of mannitol salt agar plate and incubated in 37°C for 24hr then inoculated on blood agar. The isolates were confirmed according to colony morphology, Gram staining and conventional biochemical techniques and polymerase chain reaction (PCR) to detect vanB gene. The disc diffusion testing was done to determine antimicrobial resistance including VRSA. *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) was found in 46 (46%) of raw buffalo milk. The isolates exhibited high resistance (80%) to methicilin, 75% to Oxacillin and Cefoxitin, 55% to gentamycin, and 50% to vancomycin. The phenotypic analyses revealed that out of 46 *S. aureus*, 23 (50%) were VRSA. While the genotypic identification by PCR showed that out of the 23 VRSA, 18 (78.2%) isolates had vanB genes. Results highlight the potential zoonotic risk of buffalo milk as a potential source of VRSA, which may be transmitted to human beings working in close contact with the buffalos.

KEYWORDS: buffalo milk, *Staphylococcus aureus*, VRSA, antimicrobial susceptibility, vanB gene.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
01 August 2023

Available on:
<https://ijpbms.com/>

INTRODUCTION

Staphylococci are Gram-positive, catalase-positive, non-motile, non-spore forming aerobic coccid (with an average diameter 0.5 – 1.0 µm), arranged as pairs, tetrads or oftentimes irregular grape-like clusters [1]. *S. aureus* is the most important human and animals opportunistic pathogen, among the staphylococci species and is characterized by the production of golden pigment. The coagulase test is the simplest laboratory method to distinguish *S. aureus* from coagulase-negative staphylococci; also *S. aureus* can be detected or confirmed by PCR technique [2]. Many articles have shown that several *S. aureus*, isolated from humans, animals or food processing, it is associated with healthcare-associated community-acquired outbreaks worldwide [3]. The main diseases in the animals are caused by the pathogenic

Staphylococcus spp. include mastitis, abscesses, and dermatitis [4,5].

The pathogenicity of *S. aureus* is related to its capability of producing toxins and enzymes, and thereby leading to serious diseases, such as bacteremia, myocarditis, acute endocarditis, pneumonia, osteomyelitis and meningitis [6]. It has the ability to emerge and spread new antimicrobial resistance, such as VRSA [1]. vancomycin is a semisynthetic beta-lactamase-resistant penicillin that was introduced in 1959 to treat bacterial infection; shortly thereafter, vancomycin-resistant isolates of *S. aureus* was detected, the first strain of MRSA was recorded in 1961 in the United Kingdom, it is now associated with healthcare infections. Since its first isolation in 1961 until now, VRSA has been considered as one of the main pathogens of healthcare-associated infections at hospitals [7]. In the livestock, the VRSA was first, isolated from mastatic cow milk in Belgain [8], after that, it was reported in several (wild and domestic) animals [9, 10]. It is

Molecular and Bacteriological Study of Vancomycin Resistant *Staphylococcus Aureus* (VRSA) Isolated from Buffalo Raw Milk in Baghdad

increasingly recognized in the animal world [11]. Horizontal transmission of VRSA between livestock on farms and in veterinary institutions is well recognized [12]. We report the molecular characterization and antimicrobial susceptibility of VRSA isolated from buffalo raw milk.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was approved by The Committee of Ethics Research of the College of Veterinary Medicine, Baghdad University, Ministry of High Education and Scientific Research-Iraq. *S. aureus* was isolated from buffalo raw milk samples in Baghdad governorate, Iraq from October 2019 to March 2020. One hundred buffalo milk samples were collected in sterile condition from (Abu ghraib villages) in Baghdad and streaked on manitol salt plates and incubated at 37°C for 24 hr, confirmation of the isolates was depended on the morphology of the colony, gram staining and biochemical tests [1]. The antimicrobial susceptibility test for *S. aureus* isolates was performed according to previous methods [13].

The *S. aureus* isolates were subjected to PCR analysis. Its genomic DNA was extracted by the Genomic DNA Minni Kit (Geneaid, Thailand) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The concentrations and purity of extracted DNA were quantified using a Nanodrop spectrophotometer. Gel

electrophoresis was used to detect the DNA bands stained with red safe dye visualized under UV light [14]. Agarose 1 g was used for DNA extraction and 2 g in the case of PCR products was added to 100 ml 1XTBE buffer, then boiled and left to cool at 50°C, after 2µl of Red Safe dye was poured on the preparing tray. Post polymerization (30 min at room temperature) the comb was removed post-hardening of agarose in wells. Gels were placed into a gel chamber filled with 1 X TBE buffer. The gel pocket was completely covered with buffer. Then 10 µl of each sample was mixed with 5 µl of loading dye buffer and loaded into wells in the gel. The obtained DNA products were screened for the presence of *vanB* gene genes by PCR methods as shown in Table 1, these primers were supplied by Bionneer Company, Korea and prepared according to the recommendation of the manufacturer.

The polymerase chain reaction mixture was set up in a volume of 20 µl which included: 2 µl of PCR premix (contains: *Taq* DNA polymerase, MgCl₂, dNTPs, KCl, stabilizer tracking dye and tris-HCl), 1 µl of each primer (final concentration was 10 picomole /µl) and 2 µl of DNA template then the volume was completed with sterile distal water.

Table 1: Primers used for amplification of *vanB* gene gene in *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Genes	Primer	Sequence	Product size(bp)	Reference
<i>vanB</i>	<i>vanB</i> -F	5' GTG ACA AAC CGG AGG CGA GGA 3'	430	[15]
	<i>vanB</i> -R	5' CCG CCA TCC TCC TGC AAA AAA-3'		

The PCR product tubes were mixed, and placed in a programmed thermocycler for amplification according to conditions shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Cyclic conditions of polymerase chain reactions

Gene	Initial denaturation	No.of cycles	Denaturation	Annealing	Extension	Final Extension
<i>vanB</i>	94°C for 10min.	30	94°C, 30 sec.	50°C, 45 sec.	70 °C, 30 sec.	72 °C, 10min.

Before electrophoresis, PCR products for each well were loaded with 5 µl sample. DNA ladders 100bp and 1kb (KAPA Biosystem/USA) were run concurrently with each electrophoresis run to detect the size of the amplified PCR product. Electrophoresis was performed at 70V for 1.5 hours for extracting genomic DNA and PCR products, then the DNA bands were visualized by UV transilluminator and photographed using a digital camera. All steps of PCR assays

were performed in the Department of Internal and Preventing Veterinary Medicine, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Baghdad.

RESULTS

The total isolation rate of *S. aureus* was 46% (46/100) from buffalo raw milk samples. Suspected colonies of *S. aureus* isolates appeared on mannitol salt agar as round, smooth,

Molecular and Bacteriological Study of Vancomycin Resistant *Staphylococcus Aureus* (VRSA) Isolated from Buffalo Raw Milk in Baghdad

fermented mannitol and convert colour from red to yellow (Figure 1).

Gram staining of *S. aureus* under light microscope (Figure 2). Microscopically, suspected *S. aureus* isolates appeared in the

light microscope as Gram-positive, cocci, single cell pairs, grape-like clusters. The isolates were positive for catalase (figure 3), gelatinase tests (Figure 4), hemolysis, DNase and coagulase (Table 3).

Figure 1- *Staphylococcus aureus* on Mannitol Salt Agar show mannitol fermentation.

Figure 2- Gram staining of *S. aureus* under the light microscope, Gram-positive, cocci, single cells pairs.

Fig3. -*S. aureus* positive catalase test. *S. aureus* positive catalase test.

Figure 4 - *Staphylococcus aureus* positive result for gelatinase test

Table 3: Biochemical tests of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates

Test	Result
Catalase	+
Coagulase	+
Gelatin liquefaction	+
Hemolysis	+
Mannitol fermentation	+
Oxidase	-
DNase	+

The *S. aureus* isolates of buffalo raw milk showed high resistance to methicilin (80%), to Oxacillin, and Cefoxitin (75%) and gentamycin (55%) and vancomycin (Table 4).

Molecular and Bacteriological Study of Vancomycin Resistant *Staphylococcus Aureus* (VRSA) Isolated from Buffalo Raw Milk in Baghdad

Table 4: Percentage of resistant and susceptible isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* to antibiotics in buffalo raw milk.

Antibiotic (mg)	Sensitive	Intermediate	Resistant
Methicillin(5)	9(15.6%)	1(2%)	38(80%)
Oxacillin(1)	7(14%)	4(8%)	36(75%)
Cefoxitin(30)	5 (12%)	5(10%)	36(75%)
Gentamycin(10)	19(40%)	4(8%)	23(55%)
Chloramphenicol(30)	22(47%)	10(20%)	14(30.25%)
Trimethoprim(5)	25(54%)	8(16%)	13(28%)
Clindamycin(2)	17(37%)	11(22%)	18(39%)
Vancomycin(30)	20(50%)	3(4%)	23(50%)

Genomic DNA of *S. aureus* was extracted from all isolates, detected and visualized by 1% gel electrophoresis as compact bands (Figure 5) and the purity of DNA ranged from 1.8 to 2 at absorbance 260/280 nm.

Figure 5: Agarose gel electrophoresis (1 % agarose, 70V, for 1.5 hours) of genomic DNA of *S. aureus* isolated from buffalo raw milk showed bands of DNA.

PCR employed for the detection of β lactamase enzyme encoded by the *vanB* gene showed that 18 (50%) of *S. aureus* isolates gave positive results to *vanB* (430bp) gene (Figure 6).

Figure 6- showing the PCR product analysis of *vanB* gene (430bp) in *S. aureus* isolates on agarose gel electrophoresis image. Where M: marker (2000-100bp), lane (20-22) negative isolates and lane (23-31) positive isolates from buffalo raw milk samples at PCR product

Molecular and Bacteriological Study of Vancomycin Resistant Staphylococcus Aureus (VRSA) Isolated from Buffalo Raw Milk in Baghdad

DISCUSSION

Our results reveal similar phenotypic characters for *S. aureus* as reported previously^[1]. We found an incidence of *S. aureus* of 46 (46%) from buffalo raw milk samples, which is higher than that has been observed in the Basra governorate, South of Iraq, where the incidence was 22.2 % from buffalo milk samples^[17]. Also, our finding was higher than those reported by others^[18, 19]. Buffalo raw milk could act as a vehicle for MRSA transmitted to humans^[20]. The comparatively high rates of MRSA recorded in our study may be contributed to unhygienic milking practices and the rearing of buffaloes in the study area (Abo ghraib villages). The majority of buffalo herds in Iraq are household reared, and their milk and dairy products are sold in unofficial markets. Many practices such as manual milking, unhygienic milking equipment, and milk storage and transportation may participate to the high contamination rate^[21].

Our findings regarding the susceptibility and resistance of *S. aureus* to antimicrobial agents confirm previous findings^[18, 19, and 22]. Several studies have shown that *S. aureus* is resistant to one or more antimicrobial agents^[23, 24]. The improper usage of antimicrobial drugs poses great hazards to both animal and human health due to the emergence of antimicrobial resistance^[25]. The extensive use of antimicrobial agents in food animals' production, where they are often applied sub-therapeutically for growth production and routine disease prevention, often gives rise to multidrug-resistant and VRSA strains in animals^[26]. Monitoring the emergence of multidrug-resistant strains of *S. aureus* in human and animals are essential to control the spreading of this pathogen and the related zoonotic hazard^[27]. During the last years, VRSA in animals has acquired special awareness from public health authorities, it is known that the use of antimicrobials for animal treatment can promote survival or emergence of MRSA in animals^[28].

Several techniques were developed for the detection of MRSA including phenotypic and genotypic analysis, the *vanB* gene, which is considered a genetic marker used for the rapid and direct identification of VRSA^[29]. The phenotypic analysis revealed that out of 46 *S. aureus* isolated from buffalo milk 23 (50%) were VRSA. While the genotypic identification of 39 MRSA isolated from buffalo raw milk, showed that 18(50%) isolates had *vanB* gene. The genotypic identification rate of *vanB* in the current study is nearly similar to that has been observed previously^[30, 31]. Monitoring the development of multidrug-resistant *S. aureus* in humans and animals is essential to prevent or control the spreading of this pathogen and the related zoonotic hazard^[27].

REFERENCES

I. Markey, B.K.; Leonard, F.C.; Archambault, M. Cullinane, A. and Maguire, D. (2014). Clinical

Veterinary Microbiology. 2nd. edition , Mosby Elsevier, pp. 105-120.

- II. Becker, K.; Harmsen, D.; Mellmann, A.; Meier, C.; Schumann, P.; Peters, G. and Von Eiff, C. (2004). Development and evaluation of a quality-controlled ribosomal sequence database for 16S ribosomal DNA-based identification of Staphylococcus species. *Journal of clinical microbiology*, 42(11), 4988-4995.
- III. Paterson, G. K.; Harrison, E. M. and Holmes, M. A. (2014). The emergence of mecC methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus. *Trends in microbiology*, 22(1), 42-47.
- IV. Al-Graibawi, M. A. A.; Sharma, V. K. and Al-Shammari, A. J. (1986). Microbial pathogens from goat mastitis and phage-typing of Staphylococcus aureus isolates. *Comparative immunology, microbiology and infectious diseases*, 9(1), 23-28.
- V. Caruso, M.; Latorre, L.; Santagada, G.; Fraccalvieri, R.; Miccolupo, A.; Sottili, R. and Parisi, A. (2016). Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) in sheep and goat bulk tank milk from Southern Italy. *Small Ruminant Research*, 135, 26-31.
- VI. Klevens, RM.; Morrison, MA.; Nadle, J.; Petit, S.; Gershman, K.; Ray, S.; Harrison, LH.; Lynfield, R.; Dumyati, G.; Townes, JM.; Craig, AS.; Zell, ER.; Fosheim, GE.; McDougal, LK.; Carey, RB.; and Frikin, SK. (2007). Invasive methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* infections in the United States. *The Journal of the American Medical Association*. 298 (15):1763–1771.
- VII. Khan, T.; Khan, M.A.; and Nadhman, A. (2015). Synthesis in plants and plant extracts of silver nanoparticles with potent antimicrobial properties: current status and future prospects. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 99:9923–9934.
- VIII. Devriese, L.A.; Van Damme, L.R.; Fameree, L.; (1972). Methicillin- (cloxacillin)-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* strains isolated from bovine mastitis cases. *Zentralbl. Veterinarmed. B*. 19, 598-605.
- IX. Boag, A.; Loeffler, A. and Lloyd, D. H. (2004). Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates from companion animals. *The Veterinary record*, 154(13), 411-411.
- X. Wardyn, S. E.; Kauffman, L. K. and Smith, T. C. (2012). Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in central Iowa wildlife. *Journal of wildlife diseases*, 48(4), 1069-1073.
- XI. Morgan, M. (2008). Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* and animals: zoonosis or

Molecular and Bacteriological Study of Vancomycin Resistant *Staphylococcus Aureus* (VRSA) Isolated from Buffalo Raw Milk in Baghdad

- humanosis? J. Antimicrob. Chemother. 62(6): 1181-1187.
- XII. Grema, H. A.; Geidam, Y. A.; Gadzama, G. B.; Ameh, J. A. and Suleiman, A. (2015). Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA): a review. Adv Anim Vet Sci, 3(2), 79-98.
- XIII. Bauer, A.W.; Kirby, W.M.; Sherris, J.C.; and Turck, M. (1966). Antibiotic susceptibility testing by a standardized single disk method. Am. J. Clin. Pathol. 45, 493–496.
- XIV. Sambrook, J.; Russell, DW. (2001) Molecular Cloning: A Laboratory Manual. Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press, Cold Spring Harbor, NY.
- XV. Saadat, S., Solhjo, K., Norooz-Nejad, M. J., & Kazemi, A. (2014). VanA and VanB positive vancomycin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* among clinical isolates in Shiraz, south of Iran. Oman Med J 29: 335–339.
- XVI. Matono, T.; Nagashima, M.; Mezaki, K.; Motohashi, A.; Kutsuna, .; Hayakawa, K.; Ohmagari, N. Kaku, M. (2018). Molecular epidemiology of β -lactamase production in penicillin-susceptible *Staphylococcus aureus* under high-susceptibility conditions. J Infect Chemother. 24(2):153–5.
- XVII. Khudaier, B. Y.; Anad, I. T. and Abbas, B. A. (2014). Isolation of *Staphylococcus aureus* from buffalo milk in Basra governorate and detection of their antibiotic susceptibility. Basrah Journal of Veterinary Research. 13(1), 235-245.
- XVIII. Al-Graibawi, M.A.A.; Hassan,I.Q.; Yousif,A.A. (2002). Intramammary and systemic antibiotic therapy of bacterial clinical mastitis in cows. Iraqi J. Vet. Med. Vol. 26, 153-160.
- XIX. Pamuk, S.; Yildirim, Y.; Seker, E.; Gurler, Z. and Kara, R. (2012). A survey of the occurrence and properties of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus intermedius* in water buffalo milk and dairy products in Turkey. International journal of dairy technology, 65(3), 416-422
- XX. Rahimi, E. (2013). Enterotoxigenicity of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from traditional and 539 commercial dairy products marketed in Iran. Brazilian Journal of Microbiology, 44 (2), 393-399.
- XXI. Ahmed, HS (2017). Direct detection of "methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*" from buffalo raw milk in Al-Qadisiya province using Polymerase Chain Reaction assay. Kufa Journal for Veterinary Medical Sciences Vol. (8) No. (1), 38-44.
- XXII. Elmonir, W.; Aglan, H.; Elmahallawy, E. and El-Tras, W. (2019). Antimicrobial phenotypes of geographically matched *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from buffalo's milk and clinical human cases in Egypt: potential zoonotic risks. Slovenian Veterinary Research, 56(22-Suppl).
- XXIII. Yousif, A.A.; Al-Dulimy, W.A.G. and Al-Graibawi,M.A.(2008). Some aerobic bacterial causes of clinical mastitis in cow and study some causes of treatment failure. Iraqi J.Vet. Med. Vol. 32, No. 1. 148-165.
- XXIV. Dweba, C. C.; Zishiri, O. T. and El Zowalaty, M. E. (2018). Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*: Livestock-associated, antimicrobial, and heavy metal resistance. Infection and drug resistance, 11, 2497.
- XXV. Okocha, R. C.; Olatoye, I. O. and Adedeji, O. B. (2018). Food safety impacts of antimicrobial use and their residues in aquaculture. Public health reviews, 39(1), 1-22.
- XXVI. Cesur, S., Irmak, H., Simşek, H., Cöplü, N., Kılıç, H., Arslan, U., ... & Yalçın, A. N. (2012). Evaluation of antibiotic susceptibilities and VISA-VRSA rates among MRSA strains isolated from hospitalized patients in intensive care units of hospitals in seven provinces of Turkey. *Mikrobiyoloji Bulteni*, 46(3), 352-358.
- XXVII. Awad, A.; Ramadan, H.; Nasr, S.; Ateya, A. and Atwa, S. (2017). Genetic Characterization, Antimicrobial Resistance Patterns and Virulence Determinants of *Staphylococcus aureus* Isolated from Bovine Mastitis. Pak. J. Biol. Sci, 20(6), 298–305.
- XXVIII. Moon, J. S.; Lee, A. R.; Kang, H. M.; Lee, E. S.; Kim, M. N.; Paik, Y. H. and Koo, H. C. (2007). Phenotypic and genetic antibiogram of methicillin-resistant staphylococci isolated from bovine mastitis in Korea. Journal of dairy science, 90(3), 1176-1185.
- XXIX. Ostojić, M. and Hukić, M. (2015). Genotypic and phenotypic characteristics of Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) strains isolated on three different geography locations. Bosnian journal of basic medical sciences, 15(3), 48.
- XXX. Al-Amery, K., Elhariri, M., Elsayed, A., El-Moghazy, G., Elhelw, R., El-Mahallawy, H., ... & Hamza, D. (2019). Vancomycin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from camel meat and slaughterhouse workers in Egypt. *Antimicrobial Resistance & Infection Control*, 8, 1-8.
- XXXI. Yadav, R.; Kumar, A.; Singh, V. K.; and Yadav, S. K. (2018). Prevalence and antibiotyping of *Staphylococcus aureus* and methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) in domestic animals in India. Journal of global antimicrobial resistance, 15, 222-225.